

TEST METHODS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

Hiroshi Fukuda

*Department of Materials Science and Technology, Tokyo University of Science
2641 Yamazaki, Noda, Chiba 278-8510, Japan*

SUMMARY: This paper presents some of the research activities conducted in our laboratory on new mechanical test methods and their impact for advanced composites. The first subject is an innovation of bending test for pipe-configuration CFRP specimens which applied a “compression bending test” method to obtain a more reliable bending strength value than those from 3- or 4-point bending tests. In the second part of the paper, we focus on soft-core sandwich beams where the subjects of how to accurately measure the shearing modulus of cores and how to estimate the bending rigidity of sandwich beams are discussed. The third part deals with pultruded materials that are widely used for civil applications. The mechanical properties of pultruded materials made of woven fabrics, knitted fabrics, and CF/GF hybrids are evaluated followed by their discussion.

KEYWORDS: Compression bending, Pipe-configuration CFRPs, Soft-core sandwiches, Shearing modulus measurement, Pultruded materials.

INTRODUCTION

Although mechanical test methods for composite materials are well established, there still remain some subjects yet to be overcome. A bending test is such an example, because the bending strength of CFRP coupon is strongly affected by the stress concentration due to a hard loading device [1-3]. To compensate for this undesirable effect, the authors have hitherto demonstrated and proposed a new compression bending test method [4-7] which is based on the Euler buckling of a column in conjunction with the elastica [8] whose idea is schematically shown in Fig.1

The undesirable effect of the loading device used for 3- or 4-point bending becomes more pronounced for pipe configuration because in most cases thin-walled CFRP pipes will be crushed by the loading nose rather than a bending failure. In other words, mechanical test methods for such structural components are not necessarily accurate. For this reason, we applied the above compression bending test method to CFRP pipes [9] which constitutes the first topic of the present paper. The results from an eccentric compression bending test shown in Fig.2 [10] will also be presented.

The second topic of this paper is on sandwich structures. Sandwich plates have a long history of applications to structural elements especially for aerospace use, and tremendous research works have been conducted hitherto [11]. Among them, those structures made of aluminum skin (face) and aluminum honeycomb core are drawing most of the attention and a number of different standards [12] have been established to evaluate the mechanical properties of this kind of sandwiches. Recently, CFRP skin/foamed core sandwiches have also been developed which are used in various fields such as medical applications mainly due to its X-ray transmittability with a sufficient bending rigidity. For such a relatively soft core, the existing test methods for sandwich beams are not necessarily adequate. For example, the deformation may not be consistent with the classical beam theory due to the soft core and the failure pattern may be different from a bending failure; one probable failure pattern is a crush of the core. Although there exists one standard [13] to measure the

Fig. 1 Co

Fig. 2 Eccentric compression bending.

shearing modulus of core, this standard guarantees nothing about the accuracy. In order to overcome such difficulty, this paper discusses a way how to measure the shearing modulus of core more accurately and how to calculate the bending rigidity of the sandwich beam [14, 15].

The third subject of this paper is the mechanical properties of pultruded materials. Pultrusion is an attractive composite fabrication process where endless products with uniform and arbitrary cross sectional shapes can be made with uniform quality [16]. Therefore, such a pultruded material is suitable for architectures in civil engineering. In the conventional pultrusion process, glass fibers are mainly oriented to the axial direction, which renders the products highly anisotropic. Due to this high degree of anisotropy, the lateral properties are relatively inferior to the longitudinal properties and in order to increase the lateral properties, a combination of glass mat and glass roving is commonly used. Glass roving cloth has also been tried for this purpose.

Recently, a new raw material, known as knitted fabrics [17] (see Fig.3), was developed and this material is expected to be a promising candidate for pultrusion. The advantage of the knitted fabric was fully discussed in Ref.[17] and the present paper demonstrates the superiority of such knitted fabric composites [18].

(a) knitted fabric (b) roving cloth

COMPRESSION BENDING OF PIPE-CONFIGURATION CFRPs

Compression bending

Fig. 4 Fabrication of CFRP pipe.

Table 1 Configuration of pipe specimens

Specimen	(0/90) ₄	(0/90) ₄	(0/90) ₄	(0/90) ₂	(+45) ₄
stacking sequence) ₄) ₄) ₄) ₂) ₄
inner diameter (mm)	5	3	15	5	5
0 ply : thickness 0.06mm					
90 ply : thickness 0.06mm					
+45 : 0.033mm(+45)+0.033mm(-45)+glass scrim(0.012mm)					
Carbon : Toho Rayon HTA, matrix : Epoxy resin					

Fig. 3 Knitted fabric and roving cloth.

Since the idea of the compression bending test for flat coupons was already reported many times elsewhere [4-8], it will not be repeated here and it suffices to say that we applied this compression bending test to CFRP pipes [9]. Figure 4 is the schematic view of fabricating CFRP pipes. Table 1 summarizes the pipe specimens and Fig. 5 is the result of the case with the diameter of 5mm and the wall thickness of 0.3mm. In the figure, “cb” means the

Fig. 5 Comparison of bending strengths (all types).

compression bending, “3b” and “c” stand for 3-point bending and compression test, respectively. The superiority of the present method is clearly demonstrated because the measured strength was much higher than that of 3-point bending.

Eccentric compression bending

Table 2 Prepregs and specimen configuration

Type	prepreg weight content (g/m ²)				pipe		
	0 direction		90 direction		No. of plies	Thick. (mm)	<i>E</i> (GPa)
	CF	resin	CF	resin			
A	108	57	19	19	2	0.26	108
B	108	57	19	19	4	0.54	108
C	54	23	19	19	4	0.28	77.3

If the diameter of a pipe is sufficiently large, the Euler buckling hardly takes place which led us to devise an eccentric compression bending test method shown in Fig.2. By introducing the eccentricity, the bending moment at the midspan increased, so did the bending stress.

The specimens tested are listed in Table 2 and Fig.6 is an example of the results for Type B specimens whose wall thickness is about 0.5 mm. According to our experiment, the failure stress was almost constant against the amount of eccentricity and specimen length. Thus, it is concluded that the present eccentric compression bending is a reasonable test method for large diameter pipes. In the case of 15 mm-diameter pipes, a 3- or 4-point bending test was not conducted because a reliable bending strength could not be obtained.

The compression bending, even the eccentric compression bending, inevitably incurs compressive stresses in addition to bending stresses. If the ratio of the compressive stress to the bending stress is large, it is no longer considered to be a valid bending test. Figure 7 shows this ratio and it can be seen that when increasing the eccentricity and the specimen length, the ratio of the compressive stress to the bending stress decreases, as was expected. Thus, it is concluded that the present eccentric compression bending test qualifies as an acceptable test method from a practical stand point of view.

Fig. 6 Failure stress vs. eccentricity (Type B).

SHEARING MODULUS MEASUREMENT OF SANDWICH CORE

As was described in Introduction, no suitable methods are available to measure the shearing modulus of soft cores such as plastic foams. For this reason, we designed a new

(a) Geometry of specimen

(b) Schematic view of shear test stress (Type B).

apparatus where the bias load can be eliminated. Figure 8 is a schematic view of the present test apparatus and specimen. The specimen consists of 4 pieces of core materials and 4 facing materials that are arrayed in a symmetrical manner to eliminate the effect of eccentric load. Although this type of test is not certified anywhere yet, it has been adopted by various organizations in Japan.

We conducted the test for various core lengths and thicknesses. Figure 9 shows a major result where L_c and t_c are the core length and thickness, respectively. It is interesting to know that, as far as our experiment is concerned, the nominal shearing modulus of the core exhibited keen geometry dependency. That is, when increasing L_c/t_c , the shearing modulus of core, G_c , also increased.

There is a fair possibility that the deformation due to bending in addition to the shearing deformation might have been superposed for a small L_c or a large t_c . Such a superposition may have introduced the increase of total deformation and hence, the decrease of apparent bending rigidity. To verify this, we tried two kinds of calculations, (a) FEM analysis and (b) calculation based on the beam theory with shearing deformation. The results are plotted in Fig.9 and the numerical results on G_c also show strong geometry dependency. This suggests that the specimen geometry of a large L_c/t_c ratio is desirable in order to obtain more reliable G_c values. In other words, if we conduct a test using a moderate and reasonable size of specimen, it is necessary to modify the obtained values by multiplying a correction factor. To this end, the shearing test should be done first using an appropriate size of specimen. Then, from the FEM analysis for the same geometry as the experiment, the true shearing modulus of the core should be sought so that the FEM result can fit the experimental value.

Fig. 9 Core shearing

Fig.10 Equivalent flexural rigidity vs. span, modified.

Using the most reliable G_c value, we again tried to estimate the bending rigidity of the sandwich beam whose result is shown in Fig.10. Comparing to the original estimation, the present theoretical values are closer to the experimental data although a fairly large difference between the theoretical values and the experimental data.

PULTRUDED MATERIALS

This section demonstrates the superiority of the knitted-fabric pultruded materials over the conventional pultruded materials. The mechanical properties of knitted-fabric based hybrid composites are also discussed

Knitted fabric vs. woven cloth

Table 3 Details of pultruded panels

resin	stacking sequence	thick. t (mm)	V _f (%)	orientation rate			
				0	±45	90	
VE	unidirectional	U 0° roving only	2.5	60.7	100	0	0
	crossply	C (0,90) _s	2.5	61.7	51.3	0	48.7
	roving cloth	RC (plain woven #600) ₈	3.2	58.8	50.0	0	50.0
	quasi-isotropic	Q (±45/0,90) ₃ / (±45)	3.2	□	26.6	47.9	25.5
UP	unidirectional	U 0° roving only	2.5	60.7	100	0	0
	crossply	C (0,90) _s	2.5	61.7	51.3	0	48.7
	roving cloth	RC (plain woven #600) ₈	3.2	58.8	50.0	0	50.0
	quasi-isotropic	Q (±45/0,90) ₃ / (±45)	3.2	□	26.6	47.9	25.5

The reinforcements used here are unidirectional glass roving (denoted by “U”), 0/90 crossply of knit fabric (“C”), quasi-isotropic layout of knit fabric (“Q”), and plain woven roving cloth (“RC”). The quasi-isotropic plates were fabricated by stacking 0/90 layers and ±45 layers in turn. As for the matrix resin, both unsaturated polyester (“UP”) and vinylester (“VE”) were employed. The details of these 8 types of plates are listed in Table 3. From these plates, tensile test coupons were cut in accordance with JIS K 7054-1995. To examine the effect of anisotropy, test coupons were made in the 0, 45, and 90 degree directions from the longitudinal (machine) direction.

Figure 11 shows the summary of the strength data of the knit fabric crossply composites and the roving cloth composites; results for unidirectional composites and quasi-isotropic composites are not listed here due to the page limitation. This figure clearly shows that there exists some significant difference between crossply and roving cloth reinforced composites in spite of the fact that the fiber orientation and fiber amount are almost the same. That is, the transverse (90 degree direction) strength of the roving cloth composites is very low compared to the strength in the longitudinal direction. This can be explained as follows: During the pultrusion process, a fairly large tensile load is applied to the longitudinal

Fig. 11 Comparison of tensile strength between crossply (C) and roving cloth (RC) composites.

roving and the fibers of this direction tend to become straight whereas the fiber bundles in the transverse (width) direction suffer from no tensile load and the waviness of these rovings is more severe. If some exaggeration is allowed, it can be concluded that transverse fibers of the roving cloth have little role in reinforcement.

Hybrid composites

Although the knitted-fabric pultruded GFRPs exhibited superior properties, we still need materials with a higher Young's modulus in order to apply these materials to civil infrastructures such as all-FRP bridges. For this purpose, GF/CF hybrid composites were evaluated in which $\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ knit fabrics of Fig.12 were used. For longitudinal reinforcements, glass rovings or carbon tows were inserted between the knit fabrics as shown in Fig.12. Three kinds of panels, GFRPs, GF/CF hybrids with lesser amount of carbon (GF/CF-1), and GF/CF hybrids with more amount of carbon (GF/CF-2) were prepared; some details of the panels are shown in Table 4 along with the stacking sequences.

Figure 13(a) summarizes the tensile Young's moduli for 3 kinds of specimens (GFRP, GF/CF-1, and GF/CF-2) in 3 directions (0, 45, and 90 degrees) and Fig.13(b) is for the compression test. The values calculated by the rule-of-mixtures are also shown in Fig.13(a). Generally speaking, the test data values are slightly smaller than the rule-of-mixtures values, although this difference is an acceptable tolerance. The compressive Young's moduli are somewhat smaller than the tensile moduli, which is

Table 4 Details of hybrids

□	Volume fraction (%)			relative ratio		
	V_f	V_{fc}	V_{fg}	0	45	90
□				roving (GF)	knitted fabric (GF)	
□				or tow (CF)		(GF)
□						
GFRP	57.1	0	57.1	0.55	0.30	0.15
GF/CF-1	48.0	17.8	30.2	0.37	0.42	0.21
GF/CF-2	53.4	29.4	24.0	0.55	0.30	0.15

also reasonable.

Figure 14(a) is the average of the tensile strength. In this case, the difference between the test data and the rule-of-mixtures prediction is slightly larger than the case for the Young's modulus. Figure 14(b) is the result of the compression test. It is interesting but discouraging to note that with increasing the amount of carbon fibers, the compressive strength decreased.

Concerning the strength of hybrid composites, Hayashi [8] was the pioneer to first discover the so-called hybrid effect and Bunsell and Harris [9] attempted to explain this effect from residual thermal stresses in carbon and glass fibers. A detailed review of the mechanics of hybrid composites can be found in Ref.[10].

Most of the research works on hybrid composites have hitherto been conducted in tension only but as far as the present experiment is concerned, some negative effects were observed in compression. From Bunsell and Harris' view point, this may be reasonable because compressive residual stresses exist in the carbon fibers before applying compressive loads. In addition, delamination between carbon layers and glass layers will become significant in compression. Finally, our results suggest that when applying GF/CF hybrid composites to civil engineering structures, it is very important to avoid their use in the compression-dominant region.

CONCLUSIONS

In the first part of this paper, the idea of compression bending was applied to pipe-shape specimens. Comparing to the 3-point bending, the bending strength by means of the compression bending was much larger which demonstrates the superiority of the present method. As for the bending modulus, the measured values were comparable to those of 3-point bending. The eccentric compression bending is superior to the compression bending especially for large diameter pipes although the fixture becomes somewhat complicated. Thus, the method proposed here should be a candidate to obtain reliable bending properties of pipe-shaped components.

In the second part of the present paper, a test method to evaluate the shearing modulus of foamed core is described. According to our experiment, the shearing modulus strongly depends on the specimen configuration, core length and core thickness. A methodology to obtain a reliable shearing modulus by the aid of FEM analysis has successfully been established.

In the third part of the present paper, the mechanical properties of pultruded composites are described. In light of the fact that experimental data for knit-fabric pultruded composites have been accumulated, woven roving may not be suitable as a constitutive material for pultrusion because the transverse properties are very inferior. On the other hand, knitted fabric is a promising candidate where the decrease of the mechanical properties in the transverse direction is not so serious. We must keep in mind, however, that the compressive strength of hybrid composites is rather inferior to that of pultruded GFRPs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author thanks Daiwa Seiko Co. Ltd., Toray Industries and Asahi Glass Matex Co. Ltd. for

providing a tremendous number of CFRP pipes, sandwich panels and knit-fabric pultruded materials as well as financial support. Dr. Masaaki Itabashi and Dr. Atsushi Wada are acknowledged for their designing and machining many types of fixtures, conducting tests, and preparing some parts of manuscripts. Thanks should also be addressed to many former and present students of mine including Mr. Go Itohiya, Mr. Tetsuya Watanabe, Mr. Hirokatsu Wakabayashi, Mr. Takanori Kawasaki, Mr. Makoto Yamazaki, Mr. Osamu Watanabe, Mr. Hiroshi Igarashi, Mr. Yuki Minoda, Mr. Hiroshi Takaki and Mr. Isao Watanabe for conducting tests.

REFERENCES

1. J. M. Whitney, "Elasticity analysis of orthotropic beams under concentrated loads," *Composites Sci. Tech.*, 22, 167-184 (1985).
2. W.-C. Cui, and M. R. Wisnom, "Contact finite element analysis of three- and four- point short-beam bending of unidirectional composites," *Composites Sci. Tech.*, 45, 323-354 (1992).
3. M. Hojo, Y. Noguchi, H. Furue and J. Matsui, "On the bending test method of advanced composite materials – Effect of cushion materials," *Proc. 28th JSASS/JSME Strength Conf.*, 370-373 (1986), (in Japanese).
4. H. Fukuda, "A new bending test method of advanced composites," *Experimental Mechanics*, 29, 330-335 (1989).
5. H. Fukuda, "Compression bending test method for advanced composites," *J. Japan Soc. Aero. Space Sci.*, 41, 482-487 (1993), (in Japanese).
6. H. Fukuda, H. Katoh and H. Uesugi, "A modified procedure to measure bending strength and modulus of advanced composites by means of compression bending," *J. Composite Mater.*, 29, 195-207 (1995).
7. H. Fukuda and M. Itabashi, "Simplified compression bending test method for advanced composites," *Composites, Part A*, 30, 249-256 (1999).
8. S. P. Timoshenko and J. M. Gere, "Theory of Elastic Stability," 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, 76-82 (1961).
9. H. Fukuda, T. Watanabe, M. Itabashi and A. Wada, "Compression bending test method for CFRP pipe," *Composites Science and Technology*, 62, 2075-2081 (2002).
10. H. Fukuda, O. Watanabe, M. Itabashi and A. Wada, "Eccentric compression bending test for CFRP pipe," *Advanced Composite Mater.*, 11, 193-201 (2002).
11. J. R. Vinson, "The Behavior of Sandwich Structures of Isotropic and Composite Materials," Technomic, Lancaster (1999).
12. ASTM Standards, C 271-297, C-363-369, C-393-394, C-480-481.
13. ASTM C 273-00, "Standard test method for shear properties of sandwich core materials."
14. H. Fukuda, G. Itohiya, A. Kataoka and S. Tashiro, "Evaluation of bending rigidity of CFRP skin-foamed core sandwich beams," *J. Sandwich Structures and Materials*, in press.
15. A. Wada, T. Kawasaki, Y. Minoda, A. Kataoka, S. Tashiro and H. Fukuda, "A method to measure the shearing modulus of the foamed core for sandwich plates," *J. Composite Structures*, in press.
16. J. A. Roux, J. G. Vaughan and R. Shanku, "Comparison of measurements and modeling for pultrusion of a fiberglass/epoxy I-beam," *J. Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 17, 1557-1578 (1998).
17. P. L. DeWalt and R. P. Reichard, "Just how good are knitted fabrics," *J. Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 13, 908-917 (1994).
18. H. Fukuda, H. Takaki, H. Igarashi, G. Itohiya, K. Hayashi, M. Itabashi and A. Wada, "Knitted-fabric pultruded GFRPs and CF/GF hybrids for civil use," *Proc. 3rd Japan-Canada Joint Conference on New Application of Advanced Composites*, Ueda, Japan, 1-8 (2003).